

The Effect of Customer Perceived Value, E-Service Quality on Repurchase Intention Moderated by Brand Trust in the Herbal Shop Indonesia

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Abstract:- Herbal shop Indonesia is a pioneer using gambier extraction into catechins in the form of herbs to prevent as early as possible the symptoms of impaired immunity such as colds, coughs, and others, the main goal of the company is how the products made can be recognized community and can make purchases again. This study aims to determine The Effect of Perceived Value and E-Service Quality on Repurchase Intention Moderated on Brand Trust in the Herbal shop Indonesia. The data collection method in this research was a questionnaire filled out by respondents, the Sampling of 100 respondents in this study using the Accidental Sampling method. The independent variables in this study consisted of ffect of Perceived Value and E-Service Quality , while the dependent variable was Repurchase Intention Moderated on Brand Trust. The analysis used in this study includes the Likert scale method, validity test, reliability test and SEM analysis test.

Keywords:- *Perceived Value; E-Service Quality ; Repurchase Intention; Brand Trust.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Public trust in products marketed through social media has influenced consumer behavior, starting from how to get information to behavior after making a purchase, such as statements of dissatisfaction or behavior and patterns of internet use. today social media websites are a means of trust for sellers and related companies to engage and interact with consumers, especially in the business environment. Some companies are starting to pay attention to the power of social media by creating brands of certain products to achieve repeat purchases from consumers [1]. This is part of the economic activity of all people to spend on something they want due to lifestyle, outside influences, and having income even because of a growing trend in society, and the most important thing is that there is a need that must be met, especially among adults, regarding drugs, of course. there is a BPOM examiner label [2].

In the product buying process in general, consumers will pay attention to reviews from previous buyers with the aim that they will know what the advantages and disadvantages of the product to be purchased are. Herbal medicine brand reputation is very influential in the decision of prospective buyers. Brand reputation is a very crucial asset for sellers and companies because it is related to the perceptions and associations that exist in consumers' memories regarding a trademark from time to time. Brand reputation refers to the representation of consumer perceptions of the brand's past actions, results, and future expectations, which influence consumer attitudes and behavior [3].

Based on the description above, it is necessary to have a study that discusses the effect of perceived value on consumer purchasing decisions for herbal products on social media which is characterized by public interest in herbal products from Gambir. This article examines novelty by elaborating public interest in herbs containing high levels of catechins and antioxidants which are influenced by reviews given by con. Perceived value is how a customer sees the benefits and worth of a product. This value can be anything, such as money saved, better health, or higher social status. Businesses use many ways to show customers that their products are better than their competitors. This is usually done to make the product stand out from similar ones. This is also called customer perceived value and is important for businesses to consider when marketing their products. People buy things based on how valuable they think they are. This makes people want to buy products that fit their needs and wants. Even if the person who created the product thinks it is great, it won't sell if customers don't find it valuable enough.

Marketing professional using Customer perceived make important because the idea to predict how a consumer may view a product and buy a product. The business or company can price it higher or sell more units when the perceived value of an item increases, , both of which result in higher profits. This means that marketing professionals try to increase the perceived value of goods and services by determining what their customers value most. To do this, they perform market research such as data collection, trials and surveys.sumers and the affordability of increasingly.

Hollensen (2010) argues that decisions taken by consumers begin with identifying problems followed by searching for product information. After the information is obtained, then an evaluation is carried out from the various alternative options available. Only then can decisions be made and purchases made, as well as repurchase intention. After the purchase is made, an evaluation can be carried out regarding the product that has been purchased as reference material for other consumers in the future [10].

Kotler and Armstrong (2018) argue that the form of consumer behavior that has a desire to make a purchase or choose a product, based on experience in choosing, the use of consumption desires also wanting a product is a form of Purchase Decision. So it can be concluded that the meaning of purchasing decisions is a form of consumer behavior that seeks product information and examines it which then arises a desire to buy a product [8].

Although the E-Service Quality will always seek the power of potential new sources from the brand, the main priority is still to protect and retain existing customers. Ideally, the key sources of E-Service Quality will be sustainable and enduring value. However, this is not easy, because these values can easily be forgotten as marketers try to expand their brand and add new products that are either related or completely unrelated to the brand association. The impression of the brand (E-Service Quality) is divided into four parts according to namely, User image and professional impression, modern impression and popular. [9].

Brand trust is a feeling of security that consumers have in their interactions with a brand, this is based on the perception of consumers who think that brands are trusted and responsible for the interests and welfare of consumers. Another definition according to Lau and Lee (in Tjiptono, 2014: 398) is that the trust factor or belief in a brand is a crucial aspect in establishing brand loyalty. They define trust in a brand (trust in a brand) as the willingness of consumers to trust or rely on a brand in a risky situation due to the expectation that the brand in question will provide positive results [11].

II. METHOD

The research method used in this study is a quantitative research method [12]. The data was obtained in the form of nominal numbers which were then managed using the SPSS 26 application. The research data used primary data obtained from distributing surveys. The total population in this study is the age range of 18-40 years who live in West Java. The research sample used was taken using a purposive random sampling method in which the samples taken had certain criteria from all members of the population by simple regression analysis. The criteria used were domiciled in West Java, aged 18-40 years and had purchased herbs at Uncaria Herbal Indonesia as measured by data analysis techniques in the form of instrument validity testing, regression analysis testing and hypothesis testing, as well as SPSS (Statistical Product and Product Analysis) analysis tools. Service Solutions) version 26.

This research uses several previous studies in applying the theory, first was conducted by Maria Agustin Putri entitled "The Effect of Perceived Value on Instagram Social Media on the Decision to Visit Bukit Rhema Magelang Tourism" written in 2018. The purpose of this study was to determine whether there was an influence of the indicator Expressing Positive Feelings, Helping the Company, Concern for Others and Platform Assistance regarding the decision to visit tourists. This research is a quantitative type with a survey method that was carried out by distributing questionnaires through direct messages to Bukit Rhema Magelang's Instagram followers. The number of samples calculated using the Slovin method was 100 from 2379 respondents and was taken using a purposive sampling technique which was analyzed using the multiple regression method. The results of the study show that purchasing decisions are influenced by perceived value where the variables are Expressing Positive Feelings, Helping the Company, and Platform Assistance while Concern for Others has no effect [13].

Based on the theory above into several hypotheses namely

- H1 = There is influence between the independent variable (X1) perceived value on the dependent variable (Y) Repurchase Intention
- H2 = There is a significant influence of the independent variable (X2) E-Service Quality on the dependent variable (Y) Repurchase Intention
- H3 = There is a significant influence of the independent variable (X1) perceived value and (X2) E-Service Quality on the dependent variable (Y) Repurchase Intention, moderated by Brand Trust

III. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

Table 1. Validity Test

Variabel	Question	Validity value
perceived value	PV1	0,885
	PV 2	0,799
	PV 3	0,825
	PV 4	0,794
	PV 5	0,746
	PV r6	0,778
	PV 7	0,855
	PV 8	0,874
E-Service Quality	ES9	0,886
	ES10	0,849
	ES11	0,865
	ES12	0,797
Repurchase Intention	R13	0,855
	R14	0,874
	R15	0,886
	R16	0,849
	R17	0,865
	R18	0,776
	R19	0,788
Brand Trust	BT20	0,795
	BT 21	0,837
	BT 22	0,874
	BT 23	0,744
	BT 24	0,852
	BT 25	0,746
	BT 26	0,778
	BT 27	0,805
	BT 28	0,788
	BT29	0,795
	BT 30	0,837
	BT 31	0,849
	BT 32	0,865
	BT 33	0,797
	BT 34	0,855
BT 35	0,728	

Table 1 show the tes of validity for questionnaire, it is known that from 100 question report items in the questionnaire. The Result for validity, obtained r-calculation > rtable at significance levels of 5% ($\alpha = 0.05$) and $n = 150$, rtable is 0.195. The lowest r-calculation value in the study was $0.744 > 0.195$. So, it can be concluded that all statement items are valid and can be used in research.

The reliability test was carried out using the Cronbach's Alpha technique with a total sample of 150 respondents. A research instrument is declared reliable if the alpha value is > 0.60. The results of the reliability test can be seen in the following table 2

Table 2. Results of the Reliability Test

Variabel	Cronbach's Alpha	Keterangan
Perceived Value	0,832	Reliabel
Repurchase Intention	0,890	Reliabel
E-Service Quality	0,840	Reliabel
Brand Trust	0,917	Reliabel

Based on the output of the diagram, a summary of the results of the Goodness of Fit test is made after being modified, the results of which can be seen in the table 3

Table 3. Goodness of Fit

Goodness of Fit Index	Result Value
Chi-Square	14,232
Probability	0,052
CMIN/DF	1,781
GFI	0,945
AGFI	0,922
TLI	0,887
CFI	0,932
RMSEA	0,022

- The Chi-Square value is 14.232, have good value in standardization.
- The probability value is 0.052, have good value in standardization is 0.05, good fit.
- The CMIN/DF value is 1.781 have good value in standardization <2
- The GFI value is 0.945, have good value in standardization > 0.90,
- The AGFI value is 0.922 have good value in standardization > 0.90,
- The TLI value is 0.887 have good value in standardization > 0.90,
- The CFI value is 0.932 have good value in standardization > 0.90,
- The RMSEA value is 0.02 have good value in standardization <0.08,
- vThe results of table 3 can be concluded in the estimate regression values below

Table 4. Estimation of Regression Weight Parameters

			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Label
value	<---	repurchase	,857	,208	4,120	***	par_11
service	<---	repurchase	,906	,173	5,225	***	par_12
Brand_trust	<---	repurchase	1,465	,394	3,716	***	par_32

The table above is used as the main reference for testing the hypothesis in this study. The test criterion is to reject HO if the Critical Value CR is 1.967 or the p value is less than equal to 0.05. The results of testing all hypotheses in this study are as follows:

- H1: repurchase intention has a positive effect on perceived value (0.000<0.005)
- H2: repurchase intention has a positive effect on E-Service Quality (0.000<0.005)
- H3: repurchase intention has a positive effect on Brand trust (0.000<0.005)

IV. CONCLUSION

The conclusion results state that there is a positive and significant influence between Perceived Value, E-Service Quality On Repurchase Intention Moderated By Brand Trust In The Herbal Shop Indonesia. This research needs to be developed and implemented to develop businesses in the herbal sector.

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